

Synthesis and optimization of plant-based silver nanoparticles and evaluation of antimicrobial properties

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Manuscript received 06 March 2018, revised 28 June 2018, accepted 02 July 2018

Silver nanoparticles, which have high surface areas and high fractions of surface atoms, have a high antimicrobial effect compared to their bulk counterpart. The present study showed green synthesis of Ag-NPs by using aqueous extract of bitter orange peel and silver nitrate for the reduction of silver ions to silver nanoparticles. Silver nitrate solutions and aqueous extract % v/v were respectively used at light and dark conditions, neutral pH and room temperature (96:4, 93:7, 99:1). According to design-expert methodology, at dark and light conditions, silver nitrate solutions (413 and 377 μM) and extract density of 4% could provide the smallest size, lowest polydispersity index (PDI) and highest count rate of the optimized samples. These nanoparticles were found to possess potential antifungal and antibacterial activity against *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *Lycopersici* (F16) and *Ralestonia solanacearum* (bivar 2). The results showed that the increase of AgNO_3 had a more significant effect on the size of nanoparticles compared with that of the extract concentration. AgNO_3 and extract concentration had the same effect on PDI. The optimized silver nanoparticles had more effects on the inhibitory growth fungi (*Fusarium oxysporum*) at a dark condition. The antifungal effect of the optimized Ag-NPs was greater than its antibacterial effect.

Keywords: Silver nanoparticles, bitter orange peel, lowest polydispersity index, antifungal activity, antibacterial activity, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Introduction

Many crop cultivars are affected by soil-born fungal and bacterial diseases¹. Fungi and bacteria account for more than 70% of all major crop diseases². Numerous methods are used to control soil-born fungal and bacterial diseases, some of which are as follows: (1) Physical methods are used based on disinfestations of the soil by the heat generated from trapped solar energy. However, the solarization of soil is more selective towards thermophilic and thermotolerant microbes. Actinomycetes may survive and even flourish under soil solarization³. (2) The potential for the use of fungal antagonists as bio-control agents of plant diseases were suggested by Weindling (1932)⁴, but the selection of resistant cultivars through breeding practices has been found most suitable for the control of phytopathogenic fungi, as fungicides are forbidden due to their environmental impact¹. (3) Commercial

agriculture relies on the control of plant pathogenic fungi and bacteria by chemical pesticides to protect crops against pathogens and pests. The main limitation of this method is the resistance of pests and plant pathogens against pesticides, fungicides and bactericide which are rapidly becoming serious problems.

On the other hand, chemical compounds could endanger health and environment. Nanotechnology could overcome the limitations of physical, biological and chemical fungicides and bactericides and provide opportunities for their application in medicine and biotechnology agriculture¹. Many studies have been conducted on silver nanoparticles in terms of their antimicrobial effects. Silver nanoparticles, which have high surface areas and high fractions of surface atoms, have a high antimicrobial effect compared to bulk silver. Silver nanocolloid is a well-dispersed and stabilized silver

nanoparticle solution which is more adhesive on bacteria and fungus, hence a better fungicide. As mentioned earlier, silver is known as a powerful disinfecting agent. It kills unicellular microorganisms by inactivating the enzymes that have metabolic functions in microorganisms by oligo dynamic action. In an ionic state, silver exhibits high antimicrobial activity⁵. However, ionic silver is unstable due to its high reactivity and thus, easily gets oxidized or reduces into a metal depending on the surrounding media, and does not continuously exert antimicrobial activities. In recent years, in order to produce Ag-NPs, plant extracts are used due to their rapid, non-pathogenic, ecofriendly, and economical protocol and providing a single step technique for biosynthetic processes⁶. In addition, one of the biggest advantages of this method is that a large quantity of nanoparticles can be synthesized in a short span of time. Plant extracts have relatively high levels of sapogenins, steroids, carbohydrates and flavonoids. The extracts act as reducing agents and phyto constituents as well as capping agents that are mainly responsible for silver ions reduction (Ag^+), high stability of Ag-NPs, and the size stabilization of the Ag-NPs⁶.

In this study, the production of silver nanoparticle was optimized at different conditions including extract concentrations, silver nitrate (AgNO_3) and with or without light. The antifungal (*Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *Lycopersici* F16) and antibacterial (*Ralestonia solanacearum* bivar 2) effects were then investigated at optimized silver nanoparticles.

Materials and methods

Preparation of aqueous extract of bitter orange peel:

Fresh bitter oranges were collected in Sari, the north of Iran. The peels were cleaned using tap water first, and then double distilled water. The cleaned peels were kept and dried by air at room temperature and then grinded with an electric chopper (model IKA ® MF 10 basic). About 10 mg of the powder was boiled in 100 mL of double distilled water for 15 min⁷. The cooled extract was cleared through filter (Whatman) and centrifuged 8000 rpm for 12 min (refrigerated centrifuge model Eppendorf) and filtered and stored at refrigerator (4°C) to be used later.

Preparation of silver nitrate solution:

The silver nitrate (AgNO_3) was prepared at 0.1, 0.5 and 1 mM concentrations (purchased at Merck, Germany).

Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles by bitter orange peel extract:

The silver nitrate was prepared at concentrations of 0.1, 0.5 and 1 mM (AgNO_3) and was then added to the aqueous

extracts, 96:4, 93:7, and 99:1 % v/v respectively, at room temperature. Having been covered in some foil paper, they were placed into an incubator (model IKA). Within 12 h, the color of the solution started to change slowly from colorless to reddish brown (dark conditions). The same process was repeated to the solution in the sunlight condition (20 min in sunlight intensity) until a brown color appeared. After centrifugation at 12000 rpm for 20 min, the falcon tube was washed with deionized water three times by the centrifugation. The final solution was frozen, dried and kept at -20°C for further analyses and antimicrobial experiments. The synthesis of silver nanoparticles was considered at room temperature with the neutral pH factor all along the process.

Characterization of Ag-NPs:

UV-Vis analysis:

The first sign of production and synthesis of silver nanoparticles is the color change from colorless to dark red. A UV-Vis spectrophotometer was used to characterize silver nanoparticles in the solution (Cecil model CE 7250). It is the method of analyzing the absorption spectra of nanoparticles in the range of visible light and ultraviolet wavelengths. The UV spectra analyzed the treatments at 380–750 nm with the maximum absorption band at 410–450 nm of silver nanoparticles⁸.

DLS analysis:

The average size of synthesized silver nanoparticles as well as the polydispersity index (PDI) and count rate were determined and utilized by dynamic light scattering (DLS) (Nano-ZS90, Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, UK)⁹.

TEM analysis:

A transmission electron microscope (TEM) was used to determine the surface morphology and size of the particles (Germany Zeiss 100 KV). Two samples of silver nanoparticle solution (optimum light and dark conditions) were considered.

X-Ray analysis:

The X-ray diffraction was used to determine the position of atoms together to get the desired chemical structure. The solution precipitates of silver nanoparticles were placed on a slide and let dry to create a bold layer on the slide. The XRD analysis was then conducted using Seifert XRD 3003 PD (Germany).

Assessment of antimicrobial assay:

Fusarium oxysporum f.sp. *Lycopersici* (F16) was collected at Pathology Laboratory of Science and Research Branch,

Islamic Azad University. The fungi was cultured in PDA media (Germany Merck) and incubated at 25°C for 7 days. The final concentrations of 50, 75, 100, and 120 ppm of Ag-NPs containing PDA medium were prepared and poured to sterile petri dishes followed by putting the fungus on the center of each petri. There were 6 replications of the treatment for 4 days at 25°C¹⁰.

The results of test minimum inhibitory percentage were assessed using $N = A - B/A \times 100$ equation every day and compared with a control plate.

The inhibition zones were measured until filling the control plate.

A = colony growth diameter control

B = diameter of clones of treatment

The *Ralestonia solanacearum* bivar 2 was prepared at the Department of Plant Pathology, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kurdistan, Iran. The suspension of bacteria was prepared in OD 600 nm = 0.1 (1.5×10^6 cell ml⁻¹) from incubation bacteria 24 h in nutrient agar (NA)²⁴. Using a sterile core pore delved disc of 5 mm diameter with 4 pores filled by the extract, and optimized silver nanoparticles in light and double distilled water (as control) incubated at 28°C for 24 h, we measured the antibacterial activity. The concentrations of the optimized Ag-NPs, extract and control were 50, 75, 100 and 120 ppm at dark and light conditions.

Statistical analysis:

The statistical software packages SAS 9.1 (SAS Institute, Cary, NC, USA) and Design Expert (version 6.0.5) were used for the regression analysis of the experimental data and obtaining the regression coefficients^{11,12}. A general factorial design was used when each factor had a different number of levels. So, an experiment including all possible combinations of the factor levels was developed. The general factorial design was used to study the effect of three different factors on the synthesis of green silver nanoparticles. The factors were AgNO₃ at three levels (1000, 550 and 100 μM), light at two levels (0: dark and 1: light), and extract concentrations (1, 4 and 7%). The size, PDI and count rate were then analyzed using the general full factorial. The experimental data was fitted into eq. (1) as a second-order polynomial equation including the linear and interaction effects of each factor. In this equation, Y is the predicted response, X_i and X_j are independent factors, b_0 is the offset term, b_i is the i -th linear coefficient, b_{ii} is the i -th quadratic coefficient, and b_{ij} is the ij -th interaction coefficient. All analyses were

done in triplicates and the mean values were reported. The optimal samples were evaluated in light and dark conditions for physical and chemical analyses.

Results and discussion

UV-Visible spectrum:

Silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) were synthesized at different peel extract concentrations such as 1, 4 and 7% v/v and 0.1, 0.5 and 1 mM of silver nitrate at light and dark conditions.

The UV-Visible spectrum which is ranged 410–450 nm for silver is related to surface plasmons. The treatments were analyzed by UV spectra at 300–700 nm with maximum absorption band at 436–446 nm similar to those reported in the literature¹³. The maximum absorption band at dark condition was higher than at light condition.

The optimized silver nanoparticles UV-Visible peaks were sharper at light condition and wider at dark condition. As a result, the count rate of silver nanoparticles was higher at dark condition and the PDI was also higher due to a wider peak of spectrum (Fig. 1).

Moreover, as the intensity of absorption increased, the concentration of the extract in both dark and light conditions increased as well (Fig. 1).

The color change (light brown to dark red) caused by Ag-NPs at different conditions (Fig. 1) approved the results from UV-Vis spectroscopy. The brown color of silver nanoparticles led to having the maximum absorbance in the visible range of 420–480 nm^{13–15}.

The results are very close to those of the silver nanoparticles synthesis in the literature for different extracts: *Solanum xanthocarpum* extract by Amin *et al.* (2012)¹⁶, *Coleus aromaticus* extract by Vanaja *et al.* (2013)¹⁷, *Pithophorae dogonia* extract by Sinha *et al.* (2015)¹⁸, *Cochlospermum religiosum* extract by Sasikala *et al.* (2015)¹⁹ and azadirachta indica extract by Ahmed *et al.* (2016)¹³.

The effect of silver nitrate, extract concentration and light-dark conditions on the size of green silver nanoparticles:

The physical features of nanoparticles including size, PDI and count rate were investigated. The so-called factors in newly provided silver nanoparticle suspensions were studied in both light and dark conditions using the DLS method. The majority of nanoparticles main features were affected by the size and PDI^{20,21}. The DLS was considered as inexpensive and quick method.

Fig. 1. The optical absorption spectra of silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) at dark (A1) and light (A2) conditions: silver nitrate (550 μ M), extract concentrations (1, 4 and 7%). A3 is the control sample (nitrate silver).

The pattern size of green silver nanoparticles at different conditions is shown in Fig. 2.

The first parameter which could determine the size of Ag-NPs is the concentration of AgNO_3 . The formation of stable silver nanoparticles at different concentrations of AgNO_3 gives mostly spherical particles diameter^{6,3,17}. In this study, optimized nanoparticles synthesis and their size were investigated at the range of 1000, 550 and 100 μ M of AgNO_3 .

Our interpretation of the difference between synthesized nanoparticles is the rate of nucleation reaction at dark and

Fig. 2. The effect of silver nitrate (1000, 550 and 100 μ M), extract concentrations (1, 4 and 7%) and dark or light conditions on size, count rate and PDI of silver nanoparticles.

light conditions. The nucleation reaction event happened more slowly at dark condition compared to light one which could be because of greater PDI (polydispersity index) and a higher number of nanoparticles (count rate) at dark condition. But there was not an aggregation of nanoparticles; so, the nanoparticle size was smaller.

However, the above reaction happened conversely at light condition (i.e. bigger nanoparticle size, lower PDI (polydispersity index) and lower number of nanoparticles (count rate)).

So, the energy of the system suddenly increased and

resulted in the aggregation of nanoparticles, increased size and decreased number of nanoparticles. But since the duration of the reaction was short and the nanoparticles had an identical and short history, the aggregation of nanoparticles declined.

Light had a negative effect on polyphenol concentration which was more at dark condition than at light one²². Thus, the color and size of nanoparticles solution were different at dark and light conditions (Fig. 1).

Optimized silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs):

We used RSM methodology (Fig. 2) to investigate the effect of AgNO₃, extract concentration and light or dark interaction on nano size, PDI and count rate of Ag-NPs.

The following equations are the regression models for the effect of AgNO₃ (A), extract concentration (B), light or dark (C) on the synthesis of green silver nanoparticles:

$$\text{Size (nm)} = + 62.39 + 29.00 \times A + 19.42 \times B + 2.33 \times C + 6.62 \times A \times B + 2.67 \times A \times C - 5.25 \times B \times C + 28.67 \times A^2 + 9.92 \times B^2$$

$$\text{PDI} = + 0.27 + 0.054 \times A + 0.055 \times B - 0.017 \times C + 6.250E - 003 \times A \times B + 0.016 \times A \times C + 0.012 \times B \times C + 0.039 \times A^2 + 0.042 \times B^2$$

$$\text{Count rate} = + 348.44 + 38.75 \times A + 64.58 \times B - 21.22 \times C + 13.63 \times A \times B + 6.92 \times A \times C + 4.25 \times B \times C - 13.92 \times A^2 - 146.92 \times B^2$$

According to the equations above, the increase of AgNO₃ compared with extract concentration had a significant effect on nanoparticle size. AgNO₃ and extract concentration had the same effect on PDI. However, in order to increase the count rate and number of nanoparticles, the effect of extract concentration was greater than that of AgNO₃.

Based on the design-expert methodology, the following result was gained at dark and light conditions: silver nitrate (413 and 377 μM) and extract concentration of 4% could provide particle size (50 and 80 nm), PDI (0.27 and 0.22) and count rate (350 and 304).

TEM analysis:

The size, shape and distribution of nanoparticles were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscope (Fig. 3). Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to determine the size, shape and morphology of green synthesized silver nanoparticles (Fig. 3).

It showed that particles were spherical with average sizes of 50 and 80 nm for optimized Ag-NPs synthesized at dark

Fig. 3. TEM image of synthesized silver nanoparticles at dark (Left) and light (Right) condition.

and light conditions, respectively. The particle sizes were consistent with the results of DLS (Size, PDI and count rate).

XRD analysis:

According to articles, the mentioned XRD peak for silver nanoparticles appears in $2\theta = 38.1^\circ$ and as indicated in Fig. 4, the nanoparticles produced in this study completely showed the peak for silver nanoparticles⁸.

The recorded XRD spectrum showed four distinct and well-characterized intense diffraction peaks at scattering angles (2θ) of 38.5° , 44.6° , 64.64° and 77.45° corresponding, respectively, to (111), (200), (220) and (311) sets of lattice planes of face-centered cubic (fcc) structure of optimized silver nanoparticles (Fig. 4). The intensity of the diffraction peak corresponding to the (111) plane was more significant than that of the rest of the diffraction peaks in the recorded spectrum and it can be construed from the above that the (111) plane is the preferred plane of orientation for the silver nanoparticle crystal lattice²⁷.

The XRD pattern of optimized silver nanoparticles is shown in Fig. 4. The two diffraction peaks at 38.5° and 68.64° of silver nanoparticles synthesized at light and dark conditions can be seen, which are consistent with the results of the study by Amin *et al.* (2012)¹⁶. According to Fig. 4, the intensity peak in dark condition was higher than in light condition, which is consistent with UV-Vis spectra.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity of silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs):

The silver nanoparticles showed a potent and broad antibacterial spectrum (both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria) and antimicrobial activity against diverse species due to Ag ions attack to various proteins in cells. They also enhanced the efficacy of antiseptics^{6,16}.

The antifungal (*Fusarium oxysporum*) and antibacterial

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of synthesized silver nanoparticles at dark and light condition.

(*Ralestonia solanacearum*) activities of silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) are shown in Fig. 5.

The Ag-NPs had particle sizes ranged from 50 to 160 nm. As the size of a nanoparticle decreased, the surface area-to-volume ratio increased. This would result in a better contact between nanoparticles and the microorganism body,

leading to more effectiveness of nanoparticles against microorganisms.

Despite the resistance of several pathogenic bacteria against various antibiotics, Ag-NPs had remarkable and potential antimicrobial agent with diverse medical applications ranging from Ag-coated medicinal devices, including nano-

Fig. 5. Antifungal (*Fusarium oxysporum*) and antibacterial (*Ralestonia solanacearum*) effects of control sample “A1”, extract “A2”, optimized silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) at dark “A3” (silver nitrate = 413 μ M and extract concentration 4%), light condition “A4” (silver nitrate = 377 μ M and extract concentration = 4%), respectively.

gels, nano-lotions and Ag-based dressings²³.

In this study, the antifungal and antibacterial activities of optimized Ag-NPs were investigated at dark and light conditions. The inhibitory zone of Ag-NPs are shown in Figs. 5 and 6 and Table 1.

The antimicrobial activity (antibacterial and antifungal) was observed to be greater at dark condition compared to the light one.

At dark condition, due to smaller size and higher count rate of nanoparticles or different combinations on silver nanoparticle surfaces compared with light condition, a higher antimicrobial effect could be seen.

There were significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between antifungal and antibacterial activities of Ag-NPs synthesized at dark and light conditions.

According to Fig. 5 and Graph 1, the best antifungal ac-

Fig. 6. The antifungal activity of optimized Ag-NPs at dark and light conditions. E = extract, D = optimized Ag-NPs at dark condition, L = optimized Ag-NPs at light condition.

Table 1. The antibacterial activity of optimized Ag-NPs at dark and light conditions after one day

	First day
Control (water)	0C
Extract (50 ppm)	0C
Extract (75 ppm)	0C
Extract (100 ppm)	0C
Extract (120 ppm)	0C
50 (ppm) D**	0C
75 (ppm) D	0C
100 (ppm) D	0C
120 (ppm) D	12.22±0.02 ^a
50 (ppm) L***	0C
75 (ppm) L	0C
100 (ppm) L	0C
120 (ppm) L	9.81±0.02 ^b

*Small letters were significant differences in column. **Optimized Ag-NPs at dark condition. ***Optimized Ag-NPs at light condition.

tivity was observed at concentrations 100 and 120 ppm of optimized Ag-NPs.

There was no significant difference between the evaluation days due to prohibition (Fig. 6). The inhibitory effect of bacteria (*Ralestonia solanacearum*) was evaluated at 50, 75, 100, 120 ppm concentrations on the first day (after 24 h). The results showed that there was no inhibitory effect of optimized Ag-NPs (dark and light conditions) at different concentrations (50, 75 and 100) except for 120 ppm. The anti-

bacterial effect was greater at dark condition compared with the light one (Table 1).

Conclusions

In order to inhibit the growth of *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Ralestonia solanacearum*, Ag-NPs were synthesized at various concentrations of extract and silver nitrate and in light and dark conditions. The results showed that the increase of AgNO₃ compared with extract concentration had a significant effect on nanoparticle size. AgNO₃ and extract concentration had the same effect on PDI. However, the increase in the count rate and number of nanoparticles resulted in greater effects of extract concentration compared to AgNO₃. According to the design-expert methodology, at dark and light conditions (silver nitrate = 413 and 377 μM and extract concentration = 4%) , particle sizes (50 and 80 nm), PDI (0.27 and 0.22) and count rate (350 and 304) could be provided respectively.

Ralestonia solanacearum (bivar 2) is a gram-negative bacteria and due to having Lipopolysaccharide layer (LPS), has a resistant barrier against silver nanoparticles entering. *Fusarium oxysporum* fungus in its wall²⁶. The mechanism of antifungal effect of silver nanoparticles is such that by destructing the surface layer of the regular fibers of the spores' cell walls, the cytoplasmic content leakage occurs and causes the death of the cell. This antifungal property of silver nanoparticles was reported against the vegetative pathogenic fungus of *F. oxysporum*²⁵.

It seems that in dark condition, the extract concentration was higher than in light condition and the control of *Fusarium oxysporum* as earth fungi improved. The anti-fungi effect of optimized Ag-NPs was more than that of the anti-bacteria.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Mr. Sajad Moradi and Reza Maleki for complementing this research and grammatically revising the article.

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